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Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' *Nineteen Nineteen*

Dr. Sanil T. Sunny¹

Abstract

The concept of alienation and exile examines the destructive forces that separate individuals from their homes, societies, and nature, leading to tragic situations they cannot control. This causes depersonalization, disrupting their emotional harmony with themselves, their experiences, and their society. Dos Passos explores this theme in "Nineteen Nineteen," focusing on the impotence and loneliness of individuals during total war, particularly through the story of Joe Williams. The study analyzes Joe's rootless migration, symbolizing the Lost Generation's quest for motion without direction, and examines how society's dependency on Joe shaped his identity.

Key Words

Alienation, exile, Nineteen Nineteen, Dos Passos

The concept of exile involves the forced expulsion of a man from his home or society and his separation from the rest of the community. This state may lead the individual to a tragic situation, "a depersonalization that shatters his emotional harmony with himself, his experience and his society" (Njogu and Muriiki 1). This depersonalization is, mostly, the root cause of the state of mind which is called alienation on which the individual has no control. "Alienation may be described as a psychological separation from the protagonist's accepted modes of thought, usually precipitated by some sudden impetus, whether internal or external" (Claassen 87). It is one of the most familiar concepts of Marxist philosophy that has

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entered the day-to-day language.

John Dos Passos has used this subject with clarity and freshness in his *U. S. A.* trilogy. The novels in the trilogy are *The 42nd Parallel*, *Nineteen Nineteen* and *The Big Money* and together they have twelve fictional characters. The present essay focuses on the fictional narratives of *Nineteen Nineteen* that depict the loneliness of isolated individuals, most notably in the story of Joe Williams. Joe Williams belongs to a poor family in Georgetown and as a baseball player with great skills, his community expects Joe to have a bright future but he has to give it up half of the way for his family. However, he escapes from the existing situations in his family wishing he could join the navy and see the world. It is a quest for movement and freedom but at this juncture he is pushed into the harsh realities of life. Joe moves from places to places, countries to countries and continents to continents without a cent left with. It is interesting to observe how he is picking a quarrel with the captain of a ship on the way to England. It was the war time and he was travelling without a passport. The quarrel puts him in irons on account of the suspicion that he is a German spy. It proves how wretched the lives of the American seamen were and how laws provided for the whipping of disobedient seamen. The purpose of these paternalistic laws was to assure a ready supply of cheap and docile labour and obedience was the keystone both at sea and ashore. Class was primarily determined by the material base. This incident illustrates Joe's maritime experience as one of exploitation and resistance. He understands himself to be more than simply a slave to a maritime capitalist system: "The alienated are those people who have been excluded, or have excluded themselves ... the deeply maladjusted" (qtd. in Claassen 87). Joe has been excluded from the system and he is maladjusted with the system.

He looks for a new job to begin a new life with his new found friend named Della Matthews but she is purely materialistic and concerned more about her earnings than anything else. Initially, she is not willing to marry Joe as he leads a rough kind of life:

When he kissed her goodnight in the hall, Joe felt awful hot and pressed her up in the corner by the hatrack and tried to get his hand under her skirt but she said not till they were married, and he said with his mouth against hers, when would they get married and she said they'd get married as soon as he got his new job. (*Nineteen Nineteen*, 65)

Della makes it clear that it will be difficult to afford a husband who is away from home all the time and is very particular to know the amount he gets every month. Here Joe turns out to be an outcaste again. On the other hand all the jobs Joe applies for need experience or demand high school education. In personal life, his personality is neglected by others due to lack of wealth. This is one of the reasons why many manual workers of the time seek security rather than mobility and prefer a steady wage to the risks. This suggests that a person could achieve social mobility only by earning wealth.

However, Joe finally marries Della. But it does not seem to be the end of alienation he undergoes. The very next day of the marriage, he has to leave Della breaking her wishes and dreams. Joe's fate is never to have a good time. He starts a voyage on his wedding night his relationship with Della is nearly always broken.

In Joe, all kind of soft feelings are suppressed because of his responsibilities as a sailor. But he hates his officers and messmates and he despises himself. He manages to get a passage up to New York. When he gets there it seems that everybody over New York is worried about how one would be picked up in the city without a registration card. One morning, as Joe is getting out of the subway at Wall Street a policeman comes up and arrests him for not having a card. There were laws to prohibit seamen from leaving their vessels after sunfall and from travelling on land. Laws were there to empower everyone around to catch a runaway seaman. Joe is taken to the Custom House where he can see a crowd of counter jumpers. Most of them are long shore men and waterfront loafers and the policemen do not let anybody telephone and they have only one toilet. By all means these uprooted people are "pummeled into oblivion by forces too powerful to withstand" (Njogu and Muriiki 1). Joe is too weak to resist this "cataclysmic dehumanization resulting from the cruelty of man against men" (1- 2). Joe suffers with dumb unconsciousness of how disgraceful his life is and continually packs and drops from one ship to another like a piece of cargo.

Things are different in Norfolk when Joe returns and he hardly recalls the place walking up from the ferry. He has already written Della that he is coming but it seems that she is not there to receive him in the apartment. After sometime she comes with her new boy

friend and painfully Joe realises that she has lot of affairs around Norfolk and he decides to leave her. His life continues to be that of a defeatist wanderer. He returns to Georgetown to see his parents and they are seemingly happy to see him. It is from them he comes to know that the living in New York has changed his sister Janey. On Joe's way to see Janey, Dos Passos makes the readers can feel the loneliness and alienation that haunt him:

Going down on the train to New York, Joe sits in the smoker looking out of the window at farms and stations and bill boards and the grimy streets of factory towns through Jersey under a driving rain and everything he sees seems to remind him of Del and places outside of Norfolk and good times he had had when he was a kid. (Dos Passos *Nineteen Nineteen* 169)

The city of New York is presented in terms of light, grit, noise, and speed. It seems that motion and light destroy the materiality of the tall buildings and significant human relations alike. He walks down the street for sometime not knowing where to go and then goes over to Broadway and walks down to Union Square, stopping here and there. What he experiences is the impersonality of the city crowd as well as his own loneliness within the crowd.

Janey does not care much about him and she sounds stiff and cold. She acts as if she is too occupied with her work and makes him wait till the next day. "She was nicely dressed and had her chin up with a new little cute independent tilt . . . Her voice was different. She had a quick chilly way of talking and a kidding manner she'd never had before" (Dos Passos *Nineteen Nineteen* 58). The growing estrangement with his sister pushes Joe further into alienation and stress. He feels that he is put to a side by his upper class sister. It is a horrible picture of the fragmentation of the individual relationships which subsequently made the life of Joe stiff and barren. He is excluded from the society and in return he rejects the society around him. This feeling of non-belonging towards the society is a major symptom of his alienation. It is to escape from this social alienation Joe goes out as a seaman. He continues to wander aimlessly until his life ends abruptly in a senseless barroom fight.

Joe is not the victim of occult spiritual forces. He struggles in his confused, instinctual way but he can never shift the burden that pressed him down. His sudden death which comes in a sudden

crash of oblivion is an essential factor in the larger pattern of his inability to make any warm human contacts and his persistent sense of aloneness. People around him are indifferent to and remain unmoved by his efforts to live and their relations are just impersonal. Joe struggles in his confused, instinctual way but he can never shift the burden that pressed him down. He is treated so much like a child, a servant or a slave. The society that wants Joe dependent makes him that way and then concludes that that is the way he really is. His endless shuttling between the continents on rotting freighters has become the migration and rootlessness of the American lost generation and the stupor and meaninglessness of their lives.

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